

Social Sciences and Humanities Open Cloud

Realising the Social Sciences and Humanities part of the European Open Science Cloud

Irena Vipavc Brvar, Task 6.2 leader

CESSDA Widening meeting, 5th - 6th November 2019, Skopje

Project:

SSHOC

social sciences & humanities open cloud

Horizon 2020
European Union Funding
for Research & Innovation

Type of action & funding:
Research and Innovation action
(INFRAEOSC-04-2018)

Partners: 47

(20 beneficiaries + 27 LTPs)

SSH ESFRI Landmarks and Projects
& international SSH data infrastructures

Project budget:
€ 14,455,594.08

Duration: 40 months
(January 2019 – 30 April 2022)

Project website:
www.SSHOpenCloud.eu

Objectives:

- creating the social sciences and humanities (**SSH**) part of European Open Science Cloud (**EOSC**)
- maximising **re-use** through **Open Science** and **FAIR** principles (standards, common catalogue, access control, semantic techniques, training)
- interconnecting existing and new infrastructures (clustered cloud infrastructure)
- establishing appropriate **governance model** for SSH-EOSC

SSHOC Principal Goals

SSHOC will create the social sciences and humanities area of the **European Open Science Cloud (EOSC)** thereby facilitating access to flexible, scalable research data and related services streamlined to the precise needs of the SSH community.

SSHOC will leverage and interconnect existing and new infrastructures from the **SSH ERICs** to foster synergies across disciplines and expedite interdisciplinary research and collaboration.

www.sshopencloud.eu

Expected impact

The Social Sciences and Humanities are seamlessly integrated in the European Open Science Cloud

Availability of an EU-wide, easy-to-use SSH Open Marketplace, where tools and data are openly accessible

EU-wide availability of high quality “cloud ready” SSH tools and high quality SSH data

EU-wide availability of trusted and secure access mechanisms for SSH data, conforming to EU legal requirements

State of the art Research Infrastructure in several pilot domains advanced through dedicated SSH data pilots cluster projects

Maximising reuse through Open Science and FAIR principles (standards, common catalogue, access control, semantic techniques, training)

Transition from disciplinary silos and separate e-infrastructures into cloud-based infrastructure for scholars

With FAIR data & Tools and Training Services

SSHOC Partners

ESFRI Landmarks + projects

Stakeholder engagement & dissemination

Research Communities

Technology providers

*E-RIHS is not a legal partner in the SSHOC project but we connect to the E-RIHS community through the Institutum Archaeologicum Germanicum.

SSHOC consortium covers the whole data cycle

Following the FAIR Principles

Elements of SSHOC and how work comes together

EOSC

Research (data) communities

Training

Governance

RESEARCH COMMUNITY
SCIENTISTS, PROFESSIONALS CITIZENS

e-INFRASTRUCTURES

e-Infrastructures

Innovation

Tools

Marketplace

SSHOC Stakeholders and offering

On- and offline trainings and training materials and an international cross-disciplinary trainer network

Availability of an EU-wide, easy-to-use SSH Open Marketplace, where tools and data are openly accessible

Work packages

- 🌀 WP3 - Lifting technology and services into the SSH Cloud
- 🌀 WP4 - Innovations in Data Production
- 🌀 WP5 - Innovation in Data Access
- 🌀 WP6 - Fostering Communities, Empowering Users & Building Expertise
- 🌀 WP7 - Creating the SSH Open Marketplace
- 🌀 WP8 - Governance, Sustainability, Quality Assurance
- 🌀 WP9 - Data Communities

Task interesting for data services

🌀 T3.1 – Multilingual terminology

- 🌀 Catalogue of translated metadata terminologies

🌀 T3.4 – Making Data Findable by being Citable

- 🌀 recommendations and software to make data citable

- 🌀 D3.2 Inventory of SSH Citation practices, and choice for SSHOC citation formats and implementations (M6)

🌀 T3.5 – Data and Metadata Interoperability hub

- 🌀 D3.1 – Report... - An inventory of data formats and metadata standards that are currently used and relevant for the research infrastructures currently managed by the SSHOC main stakeholders, recommendations of specific formats and standards for increasing interoperability....

Task interesting for data services

- 🌀 T5.2 – Hosting and sharing data repositories
 - 🌀 Dataverse & language localisation, domain specific metadata formats
- 🌀 T5.3 – Legal Issues of innovative data access
- 🌀 T5.4 – Remote Access to Sensitive Data
- 🌀 WP7 – SSH Open Marketplace
- 🌀 T8.1 – Governance & Sustainability
- 🌀 T8.2 – Trust & Quality Assurance
- 🌀 T8.3 – Legal and Ethical Issues

WP6 - Fostering Communities, Empowering Users & Building Expertise

Our SSH training activities

Training events

Enrich your knowledge! Treat yourself to a SSHOC training event. On- and offline. All around Europe. You choose!

Train-the-trainer toolkit and bootcamps

Use our resources to support your work as a trainer in the SSH field.

WP6 - Fostering Communities, Empowering Users & Building Expertise

Our SSH training activities

Training materials

Join our training community and be the first to know about new training materials, exercises and practical case studies.

Training community

List your institute as a training hub, meet your SSH-trainer colleagues, and deliver SSH training using our new materials.

WP6 - Fostering Communities, Empowering Users & Building Expertise

D6.1 Community engagement strategy

 A series of geographically distributed **workshops** (min. 6) - 1 from the Humanities perspective, 1 from the Social Science perspective, and 4 with cross-disciplinary.

 A series of **awareness webinars** (min 6), with the purpose of updating on specific services and to showcase practical use cases within the SSHOC infrastructure.

WP6 - Fostering Communities, Empowering Users & Building Expertise

- 🌀 *D6.2 Building expertise strategy (M12)*
- 🌀 *First version of the TTT toolkit (M14)*
- 🌀 *Inventory of existing learning materials (M12)*
- 🌀 **The mid-project SSHOC Stakeholder Forum** to showcase project progress and achievements (M18).
- 🌀 **The SSHOC Final Conference** (M36).
- 🌀 **Information sheets** and materials that can be adapted to the local context and will raise awareness on needs and solutions.

WP6 - Fostering Communities, Empowering Users & Building Expertise

- 🌀 *D6.2 Building expertise strategy (M12)*
- 🌀 *First version of the TTT toolkit (M14)*
- 🌀 *Inventory* of existing learning materials (M12) / *(draft collection tool)*
- 🌀 **The mid-project SSHOC Stakeholder Forum** to showcase project progress and achievements (M18).
- 🌀 **The SSHOC Final Conference** (M36).
- 🌀 **Information sheets** and materials that can be adapted to the local context and will raise awareness on needs and solutions.

WP6 - Fostering Communities, Empowering Users & Building Expertise

Themes addressed in T6.5 workshops and webinars:

- 🌀 Data Protection and the GDPR
- 🌀 Data Stewardship and RDM in theory and practice
- 🌀 Data Citation principles and practice
- 🌀 Data Science for the Social Science and Humanities
- 🌀 Data Science for Heritage Science
- 🌀 Text Mining for the Social Sciences and Digital Humanities

WP6 - Fostering Communities, Empowering Users & Building Expertise

You too can join our Social Sciences and Humanities training community to engage with other SSH trainers, get a sneak preview of new training materials, such as our train-the-trainer toolkit, and volunteer to host one of our workshops.

JOIN HERE

Register at sshopencloud.eu/join-ssh-training-community

Join our community!

www.sshopencloud.eu

[@SSHOpenCloud](https://twitter.com/SSHOpenCloud)

[/in.sshopencloud](https://in.sshopencloud)

sshoc@samplemail.com

